

Sports in India: Problems, Reform Measures and Remedial Initiatives:

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Introduction

Sports and Games play vital a role in our life in many ways. They help people in achieving physical fitness, mental strength, socially cohesiveness and emotionally balance. Like excellence in speaking is music, excellence in movement is sports. Thus, sports encourage us to excel in all fields of our life, be it studies or job or social relations. Besides, the statement that “the battle of Waterloo was won on the play fields of Eton”, implies that sports help to develop a spirit of sportsmanship and inculcate lasting values including discipline, hard work and patriotism in people. We are a Nation of 1.2 billion people but its unbearable to say that we stand nowhere at the world stage in sports. In last two Olympics, in 2012 Olympic Games, India won only 6 medals and ended at 55th position and 2016 Olympics, India wontwo medals and ended at 67th position in the medal tally which is nothing short of being scandalous for 2nd largest nation in the world and one of the fastest growing economies. In this post, I will try to throw light on major issues with Indian sports and potential solutions or remedial.

Reasons behind underdevelopment of Sports in India

Corruption & Mismanagement of sports authorities: Corruption has become synonymous with sports administration in India. Whether it is the most popular cricket or hockey or weightlifting, most of the sports authorities in India have come under attack due to corruption charges. Besides, the involvement of politicians in the administration of sports bodies for a very long period and controversies surrounding 2010 Commonwealth Games dented the image of sports administrators in India.

Social and economic inequalities: Social and economic inequalities have a negative impact on the Indian sport and Games. Denial of access to sports infrastructure due to poverty, concentration of stadiums and other sports avenues only in cities, lack of encouragement to girls to participate in sports, etc., have impaired the development of a positive sports culture in the country.

Lack of infrastructure: This is one of the most important factors for the apathy of the sport in India. Since infrastructure is necessary for training and organizing games, its non-availability and its access to only a few sections of the society have adversely impacted the sport and Games participation and the quality of sports persons.

Policy lacunae: For the development of any sector, formulation and execution of an effective policy is a sine qua non. This is true for sports also. Till date, the sports policy planning and implementation is centralized in the country due to the paucity of resources and the expertise by the State and local governments. Moreover, the absence of a separate ministry of sports at the union level reflects the apathy towards sports.

Meagre allocation of resources: Compared to other developed and developing countries, allocation of financial resources is meager in India. In the Union Budget 2017-18, Rs 1943 crore allocated for sports. While it is Rs 450 crore higher than the previous year, it is much below than the around Rs 9000 crore spent annually by the UK for the sports sector.

Management: The problems that are seen at management level can be dubbed as the root of all problems in sports today. There are numerous sports governing bodies in many countries, which operate very unprofessionally. This is a very common problem in developing countries. In India politicians who have no interest in developing the sport occupy top positions in sports associations. They are all given honorary positions and since they have no experience in the sport due to which the growth of that sport hampers. Sports associations and governing bodies should change their mindset and should issue serious job roles with ex-sports men on decision-making posts. National associations and federations must stop whining about the governmental support and work towards developing a saleable product.

Economic: Economics of scale is a major talking point in the sports today. Inequality in the finances is a major threat to popular sports like Football. Economic imbalances in football leagues are a major drawback in the sport today. Issues of differences in salaries across sports is causing a very evidential competitive imbalance which will have a near term disadvantage which may result in declining popularity of the sport amongst the fans.

Grass Roots: Development of Sport at grass root level should be a focus of all sports governing bodies across the world, unfortunately only the popular sports, which are country specific, manage to flourish at grass root levels, there are success stories of grass root development which nations and sports associations can boast off example International Tennis Federation's Mini Tennis Promotion and US Soccer's Grassroots' development program, which has made soccer a popular sport in a country that has popularized their national sports in the world. Development of grass root sports is the starting point of disciplined and structured atheism of the future.

Disciplinary: Discipline in Sports is a major problem in the past and even consists today. That's the reason why there is negligence in the case of Doping, Match fixing, biased selection procedures, violence in sports. These are key problems that are hampering sports.

Five Reforms measures Sports and Games problems of our Nation

Improve Sports Governance: India lacks good sports governance in all sporting bodies and improving it will be a challenging task as there are officials who just don't want any change as they are too content with the way things are going. All sports bodies must have a constitution or a code like the sports code which must be strictly adhered too. A national sports framework has to be created according to which all sports federations should work. It should specify clear rules and regulations and also helps in the implementation of these regulations such people know that violation of these rules is not an option. Proper standards have to be set for the administration people according to which they should work. This is one area where the Sports bill can have a big impact and let's hope it is passed soon.

Proper Auditing: According to the constitution of the IOA, audits can be just done once a year that too by an auditor appointed by the governing council. The same rule applies for other sports federations as well and this must change. The audits must be done by an independent body appointed by the government or by the CAG and a report of it must be submitted to the government as well as they should know how the funds given to federations are being utilized. Also, apart from auditing the financial statements, internal audits or other similar audits must also be conducted by an external independent body to ensure that rules are complied with and internal system of federation is not misusing its authority. Cost Audits can also prevent inflated bills and wastage of money like we saw in the CWG games. The frequency of such audits must be at least 3-4 times in a year.

Set Benchmarks: Proper standards and achievable bench marks must be set for federations to achieve in terms of sporting achievements. Only then will we be able to measure ourselves against the world and work towards better tally's in Olympics and other international events. Performances of athletes will have to be monitored and they will have set high target levels of performance if they have to perform at the highest level. Lack of goals is one of the biggest banes of the Indian sports as many athletes just go competitions without the intention of winning or expecting to win.

Public-Private partnership (PPP): More tie ups and partnerships are required between the private and public sectors to invest in sports infrastructure and athletes. The private sector in India has not really gotten involved with sports as they have in other nations and private funds are needed for proper development of infrastructure. The government has taken the majority of the burden and its time private companies came forward to help out Indian sports. Leagues like the Hockey India league have attracted private players and bought in money, may not be as much as the IPL but it has bought significant amount of funds which could be used to develop infrastructure and help athletes. More such initiatives in other sports will help it mobilize funds.

Start Grass Root Regimes: A lot of nations have programs where they pick up athletes from the grass root levels at schools and colleges and train them to become professional sports persons. India does not have any such program and it needs to start one immediately. A lot of talent goes unnoticed in India specially people from villages and smaller towns as there is no administration there and very little infrastructure. Identifying and training athletes from grass root levels and setting up rehabilitation and training centers for them will go a long way in establishing a sports culture in India and bring the nation glory. Some serious work needs to be done, it will not be easy because as I said some officials just don't want any change but it is not impossible. If the government takes strong initiatives and blocks out self-serving politicians and officials from the sports federations, things will change slowly but gradually.

The Union Government has taken a few remedial initiatives in recent years.

In September 2017, the Union Cabinet approved the revamped Khelo India programme at a cost of Rs.1,756 crore for the period 2017-18 to 2019-20. The programme aims at mainstreaming sport as a tool for individual development, community development, economic development and national development. The revamped Khelo India Programme would impact the entire sports ecosystem, including infrastructure, community sports, talent identification, coaching for excellence, competition structure and sports economy.

In March 2017, 12 Indian players of international eminence were appointed by the government as National Observers for the first time for the development of various sports in the country. Among other responsibilities, they assess the existing sports infrastructure/ equipment, quality of scientific backup and medical facilities at the venues of the national coaching camps and report the critical gaps.

Under the scheme of "Assistance to National Sports Federations", the government has been providing financial assistance to the recognized National Sports Federations (NSFs) for supporting girls/women's exposure, training and participation at national/ international level.

In order to provide best possible help and support to athletes in their training for the upcoming 2020 Olympics, the government approved the appointment of foreign coaches and supporting staff.

In April 2016, the Central Sector Scheme, Khelo India – National Programme for Development of Sports was approved by the government. It subsumes the erstwhile Rajiv Gandhi Khel Abhiyan, Urban Sports Infrastructure Scheme and National Sports Talent Search System Programme.

Despite the above-mentioned measures taken by the government, the sports ecosystem is of poor quality in the country. For a country of over 1.25 billion, the existing sports infrastructure is not satisfactory. The lack of world-class infrastructure and the inadequate support of the government is reflected in poor performance of Indian athletes in major international events like the Olympics. Tiny countries like Cuba, Croatia and Lithuania performed better in the 2016 Olympics compared to India. It is high time; the public and private sector should come together to lift the Indian sport sector from the present deplorable situation. Extension of Justice Lodha Committee recommendations on BCCI to all other sports bodies will be a right step in this direction.

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